

Discrepancy in libraries concerning race, gender, and the public sphere: A guided tour

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Abstract

For my Master's thesis I am pursuing a project about women of colour who are library workers, and their experiences in Norway (at work). This has to my knowledge not been a subject of research so far in Norway, and with this in mind I wanted to find out more before pursuing my thesis paper and thesis project. In Sweden the research area has just been highlighted by Milia Rahman Olsson, and I hope to keep the ball rolling further. The text here is a revised paper originally for my exam in the module MBIB4240 (Institutions Promoting Information and Culture) in 2021, where I do some background work on what I initially feel are discrepancies between librarianship, whiteness and libraries as institutions (democratic spaces in the public sphere). I explore connections of the profession's history, the Nordic welfare state, public institutions and legitimization work and policies, in conjunction with racism, sexism and intersectionality. I show how American experiences of WOC are valuable to the Nordic library context for further research. I pick apart librarianship as a profession and show how it is not only based on whiteness as a norm, but has been bluntly racist in its past, and any effort in diversity and inclusion is often, if not always, adding insult to injury. Our supposed core values as librarians are worthless mirages unless we seek to change the entire profession from its core, not just through adding laws and guidelines, essentially othering WOC particularly, often landing them the 'diversity hire', which leaves these women to take the brunt of so-called diversity work. Through reflection and discussion, I explicate the terms 'white guilt' and 'white benevolence' and what these terms have done to libraries as part of the public sphere. In this paper I show how this way of interdisciplinary work in LIS and Gender Studies is fruitful to research further in a Nordic context for the sake of our profession's validity as part of the democratic infrastructure of the welfare state. This literature review takes shape in themed subsections in its main part, before scrutinizing in a review the material at hand with my research questions in mind.

Keywords: librarianship, intersectionality, whiteness, public sphere, legislation work

1. Introduction: Background, research questions, overview

I decided to become a librarian not just because I love books – but because I have certain values that seem to align with librarianship, especially after a semester of research placement at Glasgow Women’s Library. However, I have been ruminating over a sort of discrepancy that I hope to word out in this paper. It has to do with women of colour as librarians, and their experiences. But it also has to do with the welfare state of egalitarian Nordic countries, libraries as democratic public spaces, and facilitation of this public sphere. It has to do with racism, and sexism, and who the ‘gatekeepers’ of knowledge are. It has to do with tokenism, inclusivity, diversity, intersectionality, and whiteness. This discrepancy, or inconsistency, irks me to the point where I want to do my entire master’s dissertation on this, especially after some research. My initial question, what do women of colour that work as librarians experience in Norway, led to zero results. As such, I have picked apart my initial research question and I am now following a great number of leads to answer this discrepancy that is irking me. Or at least, find out what is giving me this feeling of disagreement and smoke and mirrors.

My research questions are then as follows:

- *If any, what is the discrepancy between the values of librarianship, the experiences of WOC as librarians, especially considering libraries as institutions?*
- In which ways could whiteness, the Nordic context of equality and welfare state shape experiences of WOC who work in Norway?
- Could the politics of inclusion and diversity in cultural institutions such as the library be little more than *legitimiseringspolitikk*?
- What of the facilitation of public democratic debate and space if the facilitators are nondiverse?

Echoing off my previous academic background in philosophy and gender studies, this paper will include an amount of reflectivity.

The paper will have the following structure: once I have set up the overarching framework of the public sphere and intersectionality for the understanding of this paper and my research questions (2), the paper proceeds to spell out the design of my methods (3). For my main part then, I have separated the first half into subsections of ‘rooms’ with overriding themed literature (4). These rooms will serve the latter half of this paper for a discussion of my main findings (5), in addition the discussion will highlight experiences of the librarians in question from *Pushing the Margins: Women of Color and Intersectionality in LIS* (ed. by Rose L. Chou & Annie Pho, 2018). Experiences like these will shed light on why research on this matters, as I will conclude this paper with a summary of key points made, and suggestions for further research (6).

2. Overarching framework: the public sphere & intersectionality

My research questions stem from a main component of the MBIB4240 course; the *public sphere*. Additionally, the feelings of disagreement are brought on by *intersectionality* and the understanding of its importance particularly influenced by my background in gender studies.

“By ‘the public sphere’ we mean first of all a realm of our social life in which something approaching public opinion can be formed. Access is guaranteed to all citizens” (Habermas, 1974, p. 49). The Habermasian concept of the public sphere has saturated most of LIS research, especially European. In this section I will define what the public sphere means, as easily as possible, in a broad sense, to not overcomplicate the framework. From a LIS point of view, the public sphere is especially important (see 4.2). The entire history of the public sphere as depicted by Habermas, would be interesting to do further research on (see Conclusion), however here I deem it non-essential to grasp the concept. Although a

Habermasian concept, I find Michael M. Widdersheim and Masanori Koizumi’s explanation (2016) easier to grapple with. Nancy Fraser’s critique of Habermas’ first depiction is also a necessary means to an end for this paper. Firstly, Fraser agrees with Habermas and says the public sphere, is a (conceptual) space, it is “a theater in modern societies in which political participation is enacted through the medium of talk” (Fraser, 1990, p. 57). Although in theory accessible by all citizens (Audunson & Aabø et al., 2019, p. 774), Fraser reiterates how the public sphere and thus who was participating in this publicness stemmed from a bourgeoisie culture of exclusion based on class, gender, and whiteness (Fraser, 1990, p. 60). It follows then that “the three necessary and sufficient conditions related to publicness: openness; debate; and common concern” (Widdersheim & Koizumi, 2016, p. 592), were heavily influenced by the concerns of middle-class white men (Fraser, 1990, p. 60). Room 3 will explicate further the notion about white universality. This white middle-class androcentrism caused what Fraser has named “subaltern counterpublics” (1990, p. 67): “members of subordinated groups – women, workers, peoples of color, and gays and lesbians – have repeatedly found it advantageous to constitute alternative publics” (ibid). Exemplified today with laws concerning largely concerning homophobia, racism, and sexism as mainly additives to the main body of jurisprudence, were fought for by subordinated and marginalised groups. Albeit LIS operates mostly with the understanding that “the public sphere therefore serves as an interchange arena where private actors raise issues of public concern so that the values may be translated into and institutionalized within the system” (Widdersheim & Koizumi, 2016, p. 593). By extension, libraries are a part of the public sphere, as they are known to be facilitators of democratic debate, freely accessible knowledge, and the freedom of speech (Audunson & Aabø et al., 2019, p. 774). For this paper I will not expand on Fraser’s notions of “strong publics” and “weak publics” (Fraser, 1990, p. 74-75). Instead, I would like to introduce the term *intersectionality* to build upon the theoretical framework for this assignment.

Again, the research questions at hand are contingent on an understanding of what intersectionality entails, especially together with a master’s project ahead of me where I intend to interview Norwegian librarians who are women of colour.

“The interwoven processes of sexism, racism, misogyny, and heterosexism are an integral part of our social fabric, wherever in the world we happen to be” (Mohanty, 2003, p. 3). This interwovenness is important to understand *intersectionality*. It was first coined by Kimberlé Crenshaw in the 90’s, however the intrinsic concept of intersectionality has been around since before Sojourner Truth’s famous *Ain’t I a Woman* (Sigle-Rushton & Lindström, 2013, p. 130. Reisel, 2013, p. 92-93). In Crenshaw’s largely influential paper *Mapping the Margins:*

Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence Against Women of Color (1993), she writes: “I consider how the experiences of women of color are frequently the product of intersecting patterns of racism and sexism, and how these experiences tend not to be represented within the discourses of either feminism or antiracism” (p.

1243-1244). These women's experiences are a focal point of this paper, and my future master's dissertation, and so I want to emphasize this: "women of color are marginalized within both [feminism and antiracism]" (p. 1244). As I will mention in my methodology, it will never be enough to look at theories of racism, and theories of sexism, as these theoretical apparatuses are insufficient to describe how WOC experience these axes of discrimination as overlapping and fused together (Ettarh, 2018, p. xiii-xiv). Of course, theories of e.g class, masculinity, sexuality also come into play in intersectionality. Intersectionality is often used as a way of analysis, a lens to view people's social reality, and has become more prominent in recent years (ibid, see also *Intersectionality* in Actualise Utopia, 2019, x). However, as Fobazi Ettarh notes:

"The concept of intersectionality has been expanded to the point of meaninglessness. White people love intersectionality (...) They love it because it allows them to co-opt rhetoric around marginalization" (Ettarh, 2018, p. xiii-xiv).

When white people use intersectionality as an umbrella term for anything disagreeable, e.g in conjunction with class, it lessens the experiences of WOC and the very real discrimination they face. As a white woman, I will make a careful effort to avoid this. Intersectionality is meant to be used as a tool to show and "emphasize this complexity" (Ettarh, 2018, p. xvii), not to overshadow POC.

Quickly, I would like to add working definitions of racism, sexism, and patriarchy for this paper. In a future paper I would expand these working definitions, especially I would like to add homophobia and Islamophobia. Lynn Weber writes: "Stated otherwise, race, class, gender, and sexuality are systems of oppression" (2010, p. 23). These are exploitative relationships, where one group hold power over another by forceful control, "securing its position" (ibid). Racism is understood as oppression towards a group based on their race, here, people of colour, as they have been historically exploited and discriminated against in economically and social ways of structural oppression by whites. The same goes for sexism, as it is structural oppression based on one's gender, here, women. Patriarchy are structure(s) in society that upholds the dominating class to be men to the effect of subordinating and discriminating against women based on their gender. To sum up emerging themes for this paper, these definitions are a good indication. I think this passage from Ruby Hamad (2020) is noteworthy before the papers turns towards methodology.

"Over the course of centuries, as the proponents and beneficiaries of colonialism, whites have set the standards both for humanity as a whole, embodied in the white man, and for femininity that is designed to complement the white male and so is embodied in the white woman" (p. 16).

3. Method(ology)

As I mentioned in the introduction, my approach to the questions at hand was picking them apart, in tune with what irks me. The subsections will mirror that in the next section. In the subsections I will attempt to give a small overview of connected literature, and in the discussion the subsections will piece together like a puzzle to give myself a better view of the bigger picture that could shed light on precisely what discrepancy I am attempting to word out. Therefore, the literature review is an excellent way of giving myself context and a framework for my own future research. The subsections or puzzle pieces will act as rooms in a museum, and I will bring the reader along for a guided journey with a detective hat on. It will be important to keep the themes from the previous section

in mind, as they will be the first clues to what we are looking for with our detective's hat on and magnifying glass in hand.

4. Literature Review

The literature chosen is a mixture of literature and research that I found particularly interesting and illuminating. How did I decide what to put on display in each room? Firstly, the literature was available to me, e.g not hidden behind paywalls, and it was *able to be found*. I spent nearly three weeks researching for this paper, and all it did was broaden the search words I used, because there was so little on experiences of WOC as librarians in a Nordic context, especially considering a public sphere. This broadening was what caused my questions to split and be picked apart, to attempt to put a coherent answer with a contextual framework in place. However, as shown with the term *intersectionality*, experiences of WOC cannot be simply read together (e.g experiences of being black + experiences of being a woman in the library field). As such, there are certain exceptions to how I can bring together an overview. I do find that highlighting some literature together adds to the answer instead of muddying the waters, e.g literature on whiteness and Nordic whiteness, whereas literature on experiences of racism or sexism would muddy waters if the experiences were expected to tell us something about WOC. Secondly, the literature chosen has been referenced several places, e.g Gina Schlesselman-Tarango, Håkon Larsen, Ragnar Audunson, Chris Bourg, and Rikke L. Andreassen. There is much more literature out there that could fit under the subsections, that said, I am confident in the array displayed in the subsections. Lastly, I have done no quantitative analysis of results, as this literature review will be more of a narrative or traditional approach, where in my 'rooms' (subsections) I attempt to give insight to what *kind of* literature can be applied. I would rather give the displays space than obstruct the view with too many artifacts, and let the themed subsections speak for themselves. I am also not attempting to give a back-to-back summary of each piece of text, in that sense I am leaning towards a narrative analysis of themes rather than a pure literature review. My goal is to show in the discussion how these subsections with accompanying literature are fruitful towards the research questions and future research. The goal is not to give a comprehensive reading list but give a more thematic overview.

In the following rooms, I aim to display literature on librarianship and values, which will rely on legislations, strategies, and guiding principles to an extent. The following room will draw from this, with literature on legitimation work, democratic workings in the library, LIS and the public sphere as has been signposted, and this room is crucial in combination with the section of theory to show the overall leading argument of this paper. Continuing from an example of legitimation work and façades, the next room plunges into a display of literature about racism, whiteness, and what that entails for libraries. This is also where I expand on the Nordic context with notions of the welfare state, colonialism and race, in addition to examples of 'othering' in the public sphere. I tie off these three rooms with a reminder of Norway and racism today, and open up the floor for a debate in the second half of my main part.

4.1 Room: The values of librarianship

As much as the services of librarians in terms of the reference desk or teaching information literacy in schools is an important aspect of a librarian's work, there are some underlying values and ethics as to *why* librarians do the things they do. The introduction to R. David Lankes' *The Atlas of New Librarianship* (2011) expresses how librarianship is deeply embedded in values:

"It seeks to show the way forward for librarians in a time of great challenge, change, and opportunity. It is also a statement that you are not alone, you are not crazy, you are right: It is not about cataloging, or books, or buildings, or committees—it is about learning, knowledge, and social action" (p. 1).

This subsection will try to illuminate some core values by going through important mission statements from particularly *folkebibliotekloven* (1985), *IFLA Code of Ethics for Librarians and other Information Workers* (2016), and *Yrkesetikk* by Bibliotekarforbundet (2008). These three sources I consider especially helpful as they are official, and in the next subsection I will be covering more from *Nasjonal Bibliotekstrategi 2020-2023* (2019), however there are some passages I would like to include here as well.

To underline what I have said so far about values and librarians: "Librarianship is, in its very essence, an ethical activity embodying a value-rich approach to profession work with information" (IFLA, 2016). This shines vaguely through our public library law (*folkebibliotekloven*, 1985, §1) albeit sparse in comparison to the National strategies. A part of the mission statement by law is that "Folkebibliotekene skal være en uavhengig møteplass og arena for offentlig debatt" (*ibid*), however in *Nasjonal bibliotekstrategi 2020-2023* (2019), this is heavily weighted and given much more space (see especially pages 4-10). Additionally, *folkebibliotekloven* promotes how (public) libraries shall be free (§1. 1985). The main component of these three main sources is the values of libraries in terms of free accessibility to information for all and freedom of speech, and that librarians are to strive towards professionalism especially with paternalism and censorship in mind:

"9. Bibliotekansatte skal skille mellom personlig overbevisning og profesjonell yrkesutøvelse, og ikke sensurere lovlig materiale" (Bibliotekarforbundet, 2008), «5. Librarians and other information workers distinguish between their personal convictions and professional duties.

They do not advance private interests or personal beliefs at the expense of neutrality" (IFLA, 2016). The first time I read through these, I found it a hard pill to swallow that my personal values are not to interfere with my professional values as a librarian. These official documents are *lacking*, perhaps by nature of them being guidelines and open to much interpretation. However, as a former activist, I felt deflated and annoyed. How can I strive to be ethical if I do not align inherent values with my own? What kind of authenticity and passion would that be towards my patrons and community, if not my own? Lankes comes through and gives a better understanding what the codes and laws do not really pinpoint. The laws do underline the importance of service (free access to information) and neutrality (freedom of speech, not imposing personal beliefs), however:

"Saying that the core value of librarians is based on service is far from sufficient to guide everyday decision making. I could use an obvious example, such as if a person were to ask for bomb-making information or a child were to ask for pornography. Would you give this out (serving the request) or not give it out (serving the larger needs of the community)? If your mission is simply to inform the community, not improve it, you could well answer yes, you would give it out." (Lankes, 2011, p. 118).

The reason why I am emphasizing this, is because for my research question, *values* are important. Improvement is important. If librarians are to “arbeide for å sikre brukerne likeverdig tilgang» (Bibliotekarforbundet, 2008, 1.), that entails that to some extent, librarians are not just aiding patrons in the search for information and knowledge, but also *ensuring some sort of equal access* and have a responsibility in terms of what they put on their local displays. We are supposed to *work towards it*. Like Lankes writes: “Because we [the librarians] are engaged in a conversation, we influence that conversation” (Lankes, 2011, p. 119). Without going on about neutrality, I believe this is also an important aspect of my research question: these keepers and guides that have the *samfunnsoppdrag* to ensure access to the dubbed “demokratihus” (Kulturdepartementet/Kunnskapsdepartementet, 2019, p. 4), as they are important to the democratic infrastructure (ibid), who are they? What privileges do they have on account of their background? Why am I so bothered by the idea of mostly, or only, white people being facilitators of democratic debate? What do they strive towards, on account of what beliefs? Lankes’ book is a guiding example in terms of values and ethics, all the things that are between the lines of policies mentioned, and at least gave me a better understanding of what is at stake as a future librarian in a very detailed manner. I believe this next section will illustrate this facilitation further.

4.2 Room: Facilitators of what? Democracy & the public sphere in LIS

Already mentioned, *the public sphere* is crucial to my understanding of my detective work, and instead of explicating further here *what* the public sphere is, this section will show how tied up this theory is to librarianship and libraries as institutions. Under 2., I explained the public sphere. Building on that understanding, is this statement:

“A functioning public sphere is one of the essential preconditions of any democracy, and the libraries have served as an institution underpinning a sustainable public sphere by being providers of knowledge and cultural expressions, being agents fostering an enlightened and informed citizenry, and being arenas for public debate” (Audunson & Aabø et al, 2019, p. 774). This means that I am not wrong to draw connections between libraries and the public sphere, but moreover, it means that the values from the previous section tie in neatly with this. However, my worry of facilitation and who facilitates the “inclusion of marginalized groups, particularly immigrants and ethnic minorities” (ibid, p. 779), is somehow amplified here.

I am not here worried that libraries are a part of the public sphere’s integration work for the community, on the contrary, I agree with the library’s importance, as “For many people, libraries provide important services when it comes to information access, language training and cultural knowledge” (ibid), which in turn is important for the infrastructure of democracy. This is also highlighted in *Kulturens Kraft*: «Folkebiblioteka er ein viktig møteplass og kunnskapsarena i lokalsamfunnet som medverkar til integrering og til å bygge ned barrierar, blant anna fordi tilbodet er gratis og ope for alle» (Meld. St. 8 (2018-2019), p. 72). But if there are mostly white librarians who facilitate this process, this means that not only is there a power imbalance as a facilitator/patron, but that of a community of people with ethnically diverse backgrounds, and a white person holding ‘the key’ to their access to knowledge and ‘allows’ access to the public sphere. Audunson & Aabø et al. (2019) mention a point made by Brooks et al. (2015), “racism is embedded in libraries due to a culture of whiteness” (2019, p. 780), and whilst

they are not explicating the point of culture of whiteness, in the next section, I will, as this is incredibly important and underplayed in particularly Nordic LIS research.

Most of the recent literature on libraries and the public sphere has an overtone of worry or write about ‘the shift’ (e.g. Audunson & Andresen et al.’s *Physical Places and Virtual Spaces: Libraries, Archives and Museums in a Digital Age* from 2020), which hints towards a shift from traditional values of a library, e.g. *samfunnsoppdraget* of “self-education of the citizenry” (Alstad & Curry, 2003, x) towards “an emphasis on entertainment and marketing” (ibid), and back again to values of democracy and public space, in light of an increased digitized society (Audunson & Andresen et al., 2020, p. 8-9). What I have found lacking in the discussion of the public library’s justification of their “raison d’être” (ibid, p. 10), is whether the public library, in the public sphere, to avoid Fraser’s worries about inclusion, is using words like ‘diversity’, ‘inclusion’ in a *tokenised* (see next room) way as acts of symbolism in their legitimation work. By explaining what legitimation work is, I hope to illustrate not only why libraries are seen as important to the democratic infrastructure, as e.g. *folkebibliotekloven* and *Nasjonale Bibliotekstrategi 2020-2023* heavily strive to make clear, but also another aspect of my research questions, that *legitimiseringspolitikk* when used in conjunction with ‘diversity’ and ‘inclusivity’ makes their *raison d’être* perhaps not more than smoke and mirrors.

Legitimation work, or *legitimiseringspolitikk*, as explained by Håkon Larsen, roots in how “cultural organizations need to intensify their public performances of legitimacy in times of change, as the citizens need to be reminded as to why these organizations are important and need to be preserved” (Larsen, 2017, p. 201). The mission statements and core values of the library, in the changing times of digitization particularly, are then being challenged. One could probably argue that a big portion of research done on public libraries and the public sphere done the last ten years, is part of the legitimation work of why librarians are needed in today’s digitized society (see literature on information literacy, fake news and source criticism, e.g. Birger Hjørland (2012), M. Connor Sullivan (2019) for more). Additionally, another aspect of ‘the shift’ relevant for the public sphere, is the facilitation of “relevante kulturarenaer, læringsarenaer og møteplasser. Bibliotekene er, og skal være, åpne, inkluderende og tilgjengelige steder for rekreasjon, debatt, opplysning og kunnskap» (Kulturdepartementet/Kunnskapsdepartementet, 2019, p. 4). Increasingly, then, the importance of libraries as physical meeting places is being argued (Alstad & Curry, 2003, x. Audunson & Andresen et al., 2020, p. 17. Audunson & Aabø et al., 2019, p. 780) as part of their *samfunnsoppdrag*, or “societal mission” (Larsen, 2017, p. 206).

Further, Larsen goes on to explicate this as a “rhetorical element” (ibid). This ties in with what I meant previously by acts of tokenism or symbolism. However, it is important to stress another point: authenticity. As mentioned in the section about librarianship, the point about authenticity and passion is important to me as a future librarian – and it is also important for legitimation work. For one, some actors (e.g. leaders and employees) “do of course think strategically about their legitimation work, but they do also have a genuine passion for what they do” (Larsen, 2016, p. 3), which is important to achieve legitimacy, both an ongoing process (Larsen, 2016, p. 1), and an endeavour contingent on authenticity (Larsen, 2016, p. 3). Although I am very aware this literature by Larsen is largely about cultural work e.g. the Norwegian National Opera and Ballet and NRK, I am convinced the case with libraries and other ALM institutions funded by the Norwegian government are affected by the same notion of legitimation work, be it to get a bigger portion of the national budget and fight for the mere existence of libraries as valueladen institutions.

The last display of this room is directed towards the rhetorical element. I will illustrate what I am attempting to express by the question *Could the politics of inclusion and diversity in cultural institutions such as the library be little more than legitimiseringspolitikk?*, and albeit there is authenticity involved, I am still shifting uncomfortably in my seat. This worry of ‘smoke and mirrors’, I can at this juncture only compare to the example of “symbolic corporate environmentalism” (Bowen, 2014, p. 31-32). SCE is “the shared meanings and representations surrounding changes made by managers within firms that they describe as primarily for environmental reasons” (ibid). What Bowen says is that the green symbolism of e.g environmentally friendly headquarters is just as much of a show for the stakeholders in the firm, as much as it is in the belief of the managers that this might be good for the firm’s future.

There is a lack of authenticity and genuine value in environmentalism though, and merely the *message it sends out*. As Bowen says: “the shared meanings and representations related to the environmental activities. Some symbolic corporate environmentalism has only a symbolic effect and is not linked to improved substantive performance” (2014, p. 33). This is in effect only a symbolic relation to environmentalism to keep up a “ceremonial façade” (ibid), but in reality, it is about public relations and “discursive moves” (Skulstad, 2008, p. 196). Skulstad helps me show how this ties back to the public sphere, and not merely corporate businesses, as “visual and verbal strategies interact in corporate image creation in the public sphere” (ibid), and I firmly believe this also entails ALM-institutions’ relevancy as part of the democratic infrastructure of the public sphere. Especially as Audunson & Aabø et al. suggest how libraries are “adapting to a market-oriented way of thinking” (2019, p. 780). This tells me that comparing the SCE with *legitimeringspolitikk* and my worry that ‘diversity’ or ‘inclusion’ is just symbolic tokenism, might not be far-fetched.

4.3 Room: White universality and tokenism

Turning this back to the introduction and the image of a librarian, in this section I will display literature to cultivate further my main argument, or rather, worry, revolving around whiteness. When I say white universality, I mean what Margaret L. Andersen explicates as “Whiteness is the location from which others are defined and judged, since it is white people who hold the power to do so” (2003, p. 24). This entails that white is the norm, the standard, the unsaid – and when you deviate from this, you become “the other” (ibid). However, this is also about power, as racism is “a structure that systematically advantages Whites and disadvantages people of color” (Walker, 2017, p. 34). The latter quote is from an edited collection of literature, *Topographies of Whiteness: Mapping Whiteness in Library and Information Sciences* and is a comprehensive recent work that draws in scholarly literature on whiteness, critical race theory, racism, the history of LIS and librarianship. Several of these scholars also reference blogs, in particularly Chris Bourg’s. I find this an important point to make, and it would be a place for inquiry towards LIS scholarly literature and academics as a white place (see Conclusion). This passage from one of Bourg’s posts resonated especially for my project:

“For a profession that claims Diversity as a core value and declares that ‘We value our nation’s diversity and strive to reflect that diversity by providing a full spectrum of resources and services to the communities we serve’ to be so lacking in diversity is embarrassing” (Bourg, 2014). This, I argue is in line with Room 1 and 2, is not isolated to the US. Not just because Norwegian library values today originate from the American Public Library

(see Øivind Frisvold, 2015), but also because experiences of racism are not isolated. The introduction to *Topographies* raises a concern I share in conjunction with my project, and how acknowledging (my) privilege as a white woman, using this paper as my platform for ‘good’, I am not merely “call[ing] up their privilege as a resource” (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2017, p. 19), I am also in danger of being motivated by “white guilt” (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2016, p. 668). The term *white guilt* i.e the knowledge that your white skin offers you privilege on grounds of racism, a culpability and blame for the history of colonialism (see Whiteness in *Actualise Utopia*, 2019, p. x). What Shelby Steele calls “ill-gotten advantage” and “racial guilt” (Steele, 1990, p. 501), also brings about issues of “racial entitlements” (ibid, p. 503) and “racial preferences” (ibid) that *again* ‘other’ POC into a state of victimizing them, and in a need for white people to redeem themselves, we become “White knights” (Galvan, 2015) in an effort to be “good white people” (Prescott et al, 2017, p. 293). As illustrated by the concept of the “diversity hire” (Galvan, 2015), in which POC are a token to serve the image of inclusivity in the attempt of equality: “White people need not wonder, for example, if their achievements (a job, an award, a scholarship) will be seen as happening because of their race” (Andersen, 2003, p. 26). This leads to *tokenism*, a symbolic gesture, typically to signify equal and diverse opportunities of a workplace. Additionally, tokenism is that effort to be ‘good white people’ to avoid criticisms of “only recruiting white or other normative people” (*Actualise Utopia*, 2019, p. x). The aforementioned ‘diversity hire’, or “the diverse librarian” (Hudson, 2017, p. 218), is no more than “a corporate euphemism” (ibid, p. 219).

Donald James Hudson exemplifies this white universality, “the racially unmarked norm” (ibid), with food aisles in a supermarket: “There’s food – you know, regular food – and there’s ethnic food – you know, the kind that comes from some specific place and culture, the kind for special occasions” (ibid). To play along here, you could say that the supermarket is totally an inclusive place for different cultures then, a place where you can explore diverse foods. But in the marked aisle, ‘othered’ from what the supermarket deems as normal groceries, so it’s both special and exotic, upholding the normative ideas of what groceries should be like. At the same time the supermarket owners are ‘good white people’. Hudson’s example neatly underpins what I have said so far about white universality and tokenism, in addition to the previous Room’s display of greenwashing.

There are two more junctures in this room I would like to display. One, I would like to tie in librarianship properly, and two, I need to clarify the Nordic context.

Remember the core values displayed in room 1, as I tie in white universality with this: “In spite of the pride many libraries take in their neutrality, libraries have never been neutral repositories of knowledge” (Bourg & Sadler, 2015). There is a necessity here to comment briefly on the history of librarianship, through what Schlesselman-Tarango calls the “Lady Bountiful” (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2016, p. 667). What I found when I read this article, is not only is it heavily referenced in the works of *Topographies of Whiteness*, but it also merges gender studies and LIS. Additionally, it criticises what I heavily focused on in Room 1 and 2 about core ideals of librarianship and democracy – as the profession’s and institution’s history can be analysed with the aforementioned archetype (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2016, p. 667-668. Mirza & Seale, 2017, p. 175). Today, the field is largely constituted by (white) female librarians (Beilin, 2017, p. 82. Watson, 2017, p. 143). Not just in the US, this is prevalent in Norway too, as statistics show how an overwhelmingly 80,7% of librarians are women (Direktoratet for høyere utdanning og kompetanse, s.a). Although not showing how many of these are women of colour, in a Nordic context and the lack of research, one can just assume how many of these percent are white women. Lady Bountiful is important to the Norwegian context as the American public library values and systems were

implemented by Haakon Nyhuus (Frisvold, 2015, p. 75), and I do not think this is a long stretch. As SchlesselmanTarango writes, “white women have participated in various ‘civilising’ projects throughout history” (2016, p. 668), and libraries were (and are) a main platform of education, *literacy*, likened as a “moralizing missionary project” (ibid), white women were crucial. Stereotyping is harmful, but “whiteness and womanness are, for librarianship, no exaggeration” (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2016, p. 671). In this trajectory of colonization and imperialism, white women were perfect to advance education projects rooting in “white benevolence” (ibid, p. 672), in their roles of mothering (paternalism) and moralizing (censorship, mission statements), their roles in the structures of power (patriarchy), the universality of whiteness as a norm for rationale, morale and jurisprudence (Mirza & Seale, 2017, p. 177) was spread as white women were grooming, clothing and educating people of color how to be a civilised proper citizen of democracy (ibid, p. 175. Beilin, 2017, p. 85). Because of this archetype of Lady Bountiful, “they were also assumed to have the innate characteristics necessary to be effective library workers” (Schlesselman-Tarango, 2016, p. 673). To the same extent, these white women “infiltrate[d] and soil[ed] the profession” (ibid). Therefore, to examine the core values of librarianship like I have, and particularly this passage from the new Norwegian library strategy: “bibliotekene skal utvikle seg videre som folkeopplysnings- og dannelsesinstitusjoner” (Kulturdepartementet/Kunnskapsdepartementet 2019, p. 21), is absolutely in line with my research questions and continues to strengthen my feelings of conflict. I am not saying that Norwegian librarians, or US librarians, are keeping up the status quo of white universalism and acts of racism in their workplace intentionally. What I am saying is, is that the library tradition today is still penetrated by white androcentrism and ‘white benevolence’, e.g as portrayed using the ‘diversity hire’ (Galvan, 2015) presented.

As Norway is part of the Nordic context, I will use literature here referring to the Nordic or Scandinavian to complete this Room briefly before discussing the subsections coherently.

“The atrocities of colonialism and Nazism put an end to the official racial biological thinking in Europe and, as a consequence, ‘race’ today is associated with the historical era of colonialism, race biology and Nazism in the Nordic countries; that is, ‘race’ is associated with a part of history that we have left behind us” (Vitus & Andreassen, 2015, p. 1).

Let me unpack this citation. Whilst portraying a self-image of neutral, humanitarian and, until recently, no acknowledgement of colonialism and missionary work, this “image” (ibid) is in contradiction to historical facts: we as Norwegians were involved in colonization, and have profited from slavery (Eidsvik, 2012, p. 13-15. Lund, 2020, p.101-102). Not only did we profit economically, but as a largely white population, Norwegians benefit from white normative privilege. Wholly to the extent that whiteness is a major component of how we imagine ourselves, and how others imagine us: “To be white is to be Nordic; to be Nordic is to be white” (Lundström & Teitelbaum, 2017, p. 151). Nordic white universality has resulted in “color blindness” (ibid, p. 153), which follows from “a practical understanding that race has been relegated to the past or to other countries (...) This has resulted in the belief that a sort of non-racist utopia has been accomplished for good” (Hübinette & Mähle, 2015, p. 66). Indeed, using the word *race* is not common, to the extent where there is a “disinclination towards referencing race” (Lundström & Teitelbaum, 2017, p. 153-154) in either everyday situations or in policies and legislations. Parallel with both colour-blindness and utopia, emerges another Nordic association. The Nordic welfare model and the notions of a welfare state (Vitus & Andreassen, 2015, p. 1-2. Mulinari & Keskinen, 2020, p. 1-2) entails a trust in

the *state*, heavily taxed public infrastructure for high quality universalistic systems of e.g hospitals and education, promoting gender equality, participation in the workforce and labour unions (Lund & Nilsen, 2020, p. 8-11).

“The idea that the state can solve major collective problems, and that its bureaucracy generates freedom rather than deprives people of it, is still quite robust in the Nordic countries, despite international trends towards increasing distrust in the state” (ibid, p. 10). This is important to link with the library as an institution in Norway, and the library as a facilitator of the public sphere in the sense of ‘the open democracy houses’. However, the welfare state under neoliberalism and New Public Management is being pulled into directions of privatization and capitalism (Stoltz et al., 2021, p. 8). Particularly interesting is the rhetoric around immigrants and immigration politics to my inquiry, as “the common pattern is currently that non-Western immigration and immigrants are problematized and political parties advocating against immigration have increasingly gained a foothold in all Nordic countries” (Vitus & Andreassen, 2015, p. 2).

Often this inclination of an anti-immigrant stance uses rhetoric of a threat towards the welfare state and equality, especially against Muslim immigrants as Muslims have been categorized into “Muslim bodies” (Nielsen, 2015, p. 47). This predominantly stems again from white universality, and how “the war on terror” (ibid) fixated on brown bodies “appearing Muslim or Middle Eastern” (ibid). Again, this is othering, and the public sphere bolsters these notions, a weighty example was the mass media’s reporting and portrayal of 22 July 2011 and ABB (see Stine H. Bang Svendsen’s *Feeling at Loss: Affect, Whiteness and Masculinity in the Immediate Aftermath of Norway’s Terror*, 2015). Quite telling is this citation: “The Norwegian Centre Against Racism has documented widespread racist harassment and violence against Norwegians of colour after the afternoon of the bombing” (Svendsen, 2015, p. 133). I highly doubt this excludes librarians, both as perpetrators of racism and recipients of racism. What’s more, is how public libraries have had a heated debate the last years with the organisation *Stopp Islameringen Av Norge* (e.g Audunson, 2020). Again, let me ask: who are the facilitators of open democratic debate? How do the few librarians who are women of colour feel about their librarianship in such a white profession? We can gather that Norwegian libraries are part of the Norwegian public sphere, and by extension the welfare state. There is an increased mass of studies that enumerate how the

Nordic countries “have constructed their national identities on notions of humanitarianism, gender equality, and egalitarianism” (Stoltz et al., 2021, p. 7-8) and the impact of increased immigration to ‘our values’ of civilised, benevolent welfare structures. The rhetoric around immigrants began with the wave of workers e.g from Pakistan in the 1970s, where the

Norwegian society argued that there were “generelle problemer med tilpasningen til et nytt liv i Norge” (Brochmann, 2003, p. 141), however there were also issues that showed the opposite: how Norwegian policies and laws were not adapted to fit our new countrymen (ibid). The contradiction of these values to the bubbling Norwegian racism is absurd – but remember the displays previously. Racism is bubbling because we as white Norwegians do not deem POC as equals, as our values build on white universalism and conformity to this.

This paper is not intended to spell out the entirety of Nordic studies, these would however make a very interesting analytic lens to compare e.g Nordic library mission statements and US library mission statements about race, inclusivity, and democracy, or to compare POC librarians’ experiences with tokenism.

5. Discussions of discrepancy: WOC's experiences & the (United) State of things

Taking together these rooms, a discussion of discrepancy is unavoidable. Something smells rotten within librarianship. However, here, I would like to bring about some experiences to bolster the discussion, primarily from the collection *Mapping the Margins: Women of Color and Intersectionality in LIS* (2018). Negeen Aghassibake writes: "Muslim women who wear a veil are particularly at risk for experiencing prejudice and racism in public spaces due to their distinctive clothing, which many view as a threat to Western society" (p. 81). In addition to the day to day lives of WOC, then, is the structural foundation for the library itself, i.e being a librarian WOC in a place and system of historical white universality, backed by legitimation work and tokenism. As Teresa Y. Neely points out: "The ability to survive and thrive in the kinds of spaces that we do, to not be broken by the systemic microaggressions, tokenism, ignorance, and tired, racist assumptions, scares damn near everyone" (2018, p. 125-126).

In fact, racism and sexism is so prevalent in WOC's lives, a common thread in activism is the act of self-care. Alyssa Jocson Porter et al. cite Audre Lorde in their subsection about selfcare: "Caring for myself is not self-indulgence, it is self-preservation, and that is an act of political warfare" (2018, p. 291). This is not just about burnout; it is about valuing yourself as a WOC in a society that deems you near worthless (ibid). I am aware this is the US context, but there is nothing to be found in the Nordic context to bolster this discussion, except the recent work by Milia Rahman Olson. I have only found articles about her work, not her work herself, however the headline is striking: "Rasifierade bibliotekarier ångrar yrkesval" (tr: *racialized librarians regret becoming librarians*. Clemens, 2021). Once I saw this article, I knew there was something to validate my research questions. Quite the total extent of this, I did not know at the time, and I am dumbfounded by the amount of Nordic LIS research done on the public sphere, without the proper inquiry of how the American library values interact with the Nordic welfare state, forgetting the archetypes of white benevolence in education and civilising projects, in assumptions of a sort of utopian state where race is not a factor in people's lives. As much as I am convinced in most of the authenticity in legitimation work on behalf of why libraries should exist and are an important part of democratic infrastructure, I am now also convinced that the 'diversity hire' is a problem in librarianship. I do not want to expunge any whiteness from my behalf in this project, and I do not think that would be the way to go. In several pieces of literature, including Lankes', the importance of activism and serving the entire community are driven of intention not just rooted in white guilt or white benevolence.

However, as Hudson showed with the example of the supermarket, it is shown that we as white people in attempt to be inclusive, are in effect often othering and adding insult to injury. If we are to strive towards improvement, our values need to be grounded in something else than our current ideas of static traditional library values, as their roots run deep in subordination and discrimination. Without addressing the foundations of library functions, our activism and service in the name of freedom of speech and facilitation of the democratic open space, fall short. To be blunt: accounts of integration, working with immigrant women, diversity and inclusivity, in both laws and mission statements are putting icing on a cake compounded of valueless principles. Returning to my research questions, the rooms have shown that there *is* smoke and mirrors, both intentional and unintentional., Alanna Aiko Moore and Jan Estrellado bring up this account from a librarian:

“Sometimes I wonder how radical I can be if our structures perpetuate racism, sexism, homophobia, heteronormativity, fat phobia, ableism etc. Just because we are in library positions doesn’t mean we are seen or heard. I am keenly aware that I’m largely operating in a white world” (2018, p. 372).

I am still wondering this, and I’m white – how radical can I be as a librarian, e.g how much can I strive towards improvement as a former activist and a future librarian who, until recently, saw the profession of librarianship as a perfect combination of my passions and moral values? “The LIS field is sometimes described as a social justice field (...) Practices, though, do not always align well with beliefs” (Minter & Chamblee-Smith, 2018, p. 236). By and large, how do I operate as a white woman in LIS without perpetuating what I have laid out in the subsections? Hopefully I will continue my research towards a master’s dissertation and avoid the growing feeling of white guilt. The issues I raised in the introduction then, about who these facilitators of the open democratic debate are, should be an inward reflection. It’s future me, a Nordic white woman intending to do good.

6. Conclusion: summary and suggestions for further research

To sum up the impressions so far, I would like to cite Ruby Hamad, as I did prior to 3. Method(ology): “Although strides in legal rights and some gains in ‘diversity’ and representation have been made, what our society has yet to confront seriously is what I believe is the greatest obstacle to liberation and equity: the conscious and unconscious biases against women of color that we all carry and that are shaped and cemented by years of socialization into a system that is fundamentally racist and sexist” (Hamad, 2020, p. 17).

These rooms have shown that picking apart my initial worries and feelings of discrepancies are productive themes for research. I also feel less ignorant in matters of whiteness in librarianship, and more aware of issues that WOC face as librarians. Here I would like to note that we have to avoid *essentialism*, i.e generalising WOC as a group that experience the same discrimination on account of their coloured skin and being women, as this reduces the purpose of intersectionality. Black women and Arab women do not face the same types of prejudices. Neither do Asian women as a generalised group, as Asian in itself is a very lacking description of the women coming from an array of backgrounds: Indian, Chinese, Japanese, Pakistani etc.

Additionally, as Chandra Mohanty reiterates in *Feminism without Borders* (2003): one must avoid an othering in conjuring notions of us versus them when you work towards solidarity and inclusion, especially with colonisation in mind as a white researcher (p. 7. Rosland, 2008, p. 199-200). Throughout this paper I have pointed out several areas and topics which would be interesting and valuable to research. I have no guarantee that aspects of these have not been under scrutiny already, but I *can* guarantee that any venture into the Nordic context of LIS and intersectionality will bear fruit. This paper has shown that. I would find it very interesting to read something about the academics of LIS research, and what is deemed scholarly literature, and who writes the scholarly research presented in journals. Studies about what the LIS students have on their curriculum in effort to advance values and what students know about the history of librarianship, in tune with Lady Bountiful, would be *very* interesting, as I have only briefly encountered topics of racism, sexism and intersectionality, without any focus on white universality and how that can injure our work with immigrant women (as this is particularly weighted in curriculum about diversity and activism). Research should also delve deep into statistics and find out who the librarians *are*.

We know an approximate gender imbalance, but the Nordic context lacks significantly in comparison to the American one. Studies on this could also neatly tie up threads with the facilitators of the public sphere and the

welfare state. I would be inclined to add that I am interested in a comparison of mission statements between Nordic countries and the tokenised ‘diversity hire’, and ‘dannelsesopdraget’, in conjunction with class and whiteness. Moore & Estrellado poignantly state:

“Women of color librarians see and relate to the world in unique ways because of their different social locations and lived experiences. Research on this topic is important because it centers the perspective of women of color, using their own voices and stories” (2018, p. 350). This is what I want to work towards – letting Norwegian WOC who are librarians speak their truth as bluntly as possible in my own academic LIS context as a white woman, without victimisation, without adding insult to injury. By doing this, maybe I can lessen the feelings of discrepancy of future LIS students and increase the attention towards true improvement not grounded in white benevolence.

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